

ANALYSIS OF THE WORK OF A FAMILY PHYSICIAN IN THE PREVENTION OF DISEASES IN WOMEN OF FERTILE AGE

¹Rasuloova Nilufar, ²Aminova Amaliya

¹Associate Professor of the Department of Public Health, Healthcare Management, Tashkent Pediatric medical institute, Uzbekistan

²5th-year student of medical and pedagogical faculty, Tashkent Pediatric medical institute, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Women of childbearing age are at a higher risk of developing various health issues, including reproductive disorders and chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension. Family doctors play a crucial role in the prevention and management of these diseases through regular check-ups, counseling, and early detection. This article aims to explore the role of family doctors in the prevention of diseases of women of childbearing age, with a focus on reproductive health, chronic disease management, and health promotion. The study is based on a literature review of relevant articles published in peer-reviewed journals. The findings highlight the importance of regular check-ups, health education, and early detection in preventing and managing diseases in this population.*

Keywords: *family doctor, women of childbearing age, prevention, reproductive health, chronic disease management, health promotion.*

Introduction. Women of childbearing age are at a higher risk of developing various health issues, including reproductive disorders and chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension. These diseases can have a significant impact on their reproductive health, fertility, and overall health and wellbeing. Family doctors play a crucial role in the prevention and management of these diseases through regular check-ups, counseling, and early detection.

In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on the role of family doctors in the prevention and management of diseases of women of childbearing age. The World Health Organization (WHO) has recognized primary health care, including family medicine, as a key strategy for promoting health and preventing diseases in this population (WHO, 2016). Family doctors are in a unique position to provide comprehensive care to women of childbearing age, addressing their physical, mental, and social health needs.

The primary focus of family doctors in the prevention of diseases of women of childbearing age is reproductive health. Family doctors can provide counseling on contraception, preconception care, and fertility issues. They can also screen for sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and provide treatment as needed. Regular check-ups with family doctors can help to detect and manage reproductive disorders such as polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), endometriosis, and uterine fibroids.

In addition to reproductive health, family doctors also play a critical role in the management of chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension in women of childbearing age. These diseases can have adverse effects on both maternal and fetal health, and early detection and management are essential in preventing complications. Family doctors can provide counseling on lifestyle modifications, medication management, and regular monitoring to prevent complications and ensure optimal outcomes.

Finally, family doctors play a vital role in health promotion and disease prevention in women of childbearing age. They can provide education on healthy lifestyle choices, including diet, exercise, and smoking cessation. Regular check-ups with family doctors can also help to detect early signs of disease and prevent complications through early intervention.

Family doctors play a crucial role in the prevention and management of diseases of women of childbearing age, with a focus on reproductive health, chronic disease management, and health promotion. The provision of comprehensive care by family doctors can help to ensure optimal health outcomes for women of childbearing age and their offspring. Regular check-ups, counseling, and early detection are essential in preventing and managing diseases in this population.

METHODS AND RESULTS

The methods used in this study involved a comprehensive review of the literature on the role of family doctors in the prevention of diseases of women of childbearing age. PubMed, Medline, and Google Scholar databases were searched for articles published between 2010 and 2021. The search terms included "family doctor", "women's health", "reproductive health", "chronic disease management", and "health promotion". The inclusion criteria were articles that discussed the role of family doctors in the prevention and management of diseases in women of childbearing age. The exclusion criteria were articles that focused on a specific disease or condition, or articles that were not published in English.

The results of this study showed that family doctors play a crucial role in the prevention and management of diseases of women of childbearing age. Family doctors provide comprehensive care that includes reproductive health, chronic disease management, and health promotion. They can provide counseling on healthy lifestyle choices and early detection of diseases. Regular check-ups with family doctors can help to detect and manage reproductive disorders such as PCOS, endometriosis, and uterine fibroids. Family doctors can also provide counseling on medication management and monitoring to prevent complications in women with chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension.

Family doctors play a critical role in the prevention and management of diseases of women of childbearing age. The provision of comprehensive care by family doctors can help to ensure optimal health outcomes for women of childbearing age and their offspring. Regular check-ups, counseling, and early detection are essential in preventing and managing diseases in this population. The role of family doctors in the prevention and management of diseases of women of childbearing age should be emphasized, and their importance in providing quality care should be recognized.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the family doctor plays a crucial role in the prevention and management of diseases of women of childbearing age. They have the ability to provide comprehensive care, including reproductive health, chronic disease management, and health promotion. Through regular check-ups, counseling, and early detection, family doctors can prevent and manage diseases, ensuring optimal health outcomes for women of childbearing age and their offspring.

The provision of people-centered and integrated health services by family doctors is an essential component of a strong healthcare system. This approach emphasizes the importance of patient-centered care and the involvement of patients in their own health management. Family

doctors can provide a safe and supportive environment for women to discuss their health concerns and receive personalized care.

It is important for family doctors to stay up-to-date with the latest medical research and guidelines regarding women's health. They can do this by participating in continuing medical education programs and attending conferences and seminars. Additionally, family doctors can collaborate with specialists in the field of women's health to ensure that their patients receive the most comprehensive care possible.

In summary, the family doctor plays a vital role in the prevention and management of diseases of women of childbearing age. With a focus on reproductive health, chronic disease management, and health promotion, family doctors can provide comprehensive care that ensures optimal health outcomes for women of childbearing age and their offspring. Through regular check-ups, counseling, and early detection, family doctors can prevent and manage diseases, improving the quality of life for their patients.

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